

Hybrid Trial & External Control Trial

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The randomized clinical trial of a treatment versus a control arm is typically the gold standard for generating confirmatory evidence of safety and efficacy. However, there are many settings where randomizing patients to a control arm therapy may be infeasible or unethical. Examples include rare diseases, pediatrics, or any other settings with high unmet medical need. There are clinical trial designs that supplement or replace the control arm that would be a randomized trial with data from sources outside the clinical trial.

A **hybrid trial** is a randomized clinical trial where the randomization ratio often favors the treatment arm and data from outside the trial are used to augment the control arm [1].

An **externally controlled trial** assigns all patients to the treatment and uses data from outside the trial to replace the control arm entirely [2].

The data from outside the trial, i.e., the external control data may come from other clinical trials, diseases registries, claims data, or other real world data sources.

When evaluating the use of external data in these trial designs, important considerations include the data quality, the treatments received, and similarity in terms of the patient characteristics and the ascertainment of endpoints.

Reference:

[1] Vents, S., Khozin, S., Louv, B. et al. The design and evaluation of hybrid controlled trials that leverage external data and randomization. *Nat Commun* 13, 5783 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-33192-1>

[2] FDA Draft Guidance: Considerations for the Design and Conduct of Externally Controlled Trials for Drug and Biological Products, February 2023

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10939262

Immortal Time Bias – why do OSCAR winners live longer?

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In observational studies and clinical trials with survival endpoints, there may be a delay or waiting period before a subject begins to receive a treatment. For example, a patient with kidney failure has to be alive until the day of kidney transplantation, thus the life expectancy of the transplanted group patient is artificially prolonged compared to those un-transplanted.

An OSCAR winner needs to establish a successful career to receive the OSCAR award, if you assume receiving OSCAR as a treatment [1].

This delay period is called “**immortal time**” because, by design, subjects in the treated group must survive a period of time in order to receive the treatment. Ignoring this selection process will lead to bias in the treatment effect estimate, which is called “**immortal time bias**” [2].

Various methods, including Cox model with time-varying covariates, landmark analysis, have been used to correct for the bias [3].

[1] Sylvestre MP, Huszti E, Hanley JA. Do OSCAR winners live longer than less successful peers? A reanalysis of the evidence. *Ann Intern Med*. 2006 Sep 5;145(5):361-3; discussion 392. doi: 10.7326/0003-4819-145-5-200609050-00009.

[2] Karim ME, Gustafson P, Petkau J, Tremlett H; Comparison of Statistical Approaches for Dealing With Immortal Time Bias in Drug Effectiveness Studies. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2016 Aug 15;184(4):325-35. doi: 10.1093/aje/kww445.

[3] Cho, I.S., Chae, Y.R., Kim, J.H. et al. Statistical methods for elimination of guarantee-time bias in cohort studies: a simulation study. *BMC Med Res Methodol* 17, 126 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-017-0405-6>

Biostat Bytes

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10939267